

Structuring Ontologies for Bayesian Reasoning in LLM Contexts

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Abstract—Large Language Models (LLMs) have proven to be effective tools for generating coherent text and supporting decision making across domains. However, in complex settings such as healthcare, decision making requires reasoning under uncertainty, causal inference, and the ability to quantify risks or probabilities related to specific events. These capabilities are not fully supported by LLMs, in part due to their lack of an explicit, structured knowledge domain.

An emerging line of research seeks to address this limitation by equipping LLMs with symbolic knowledge through ontologies. Some approaches even leverage LLMs to automatically generate ontologies from domain-specific documents by identifying classes, relationships, and properties. However, these automatically generated ontologies often exhibit high structural variability, making it difficult to quantify decisions or compute probabilistic outcomes, especially in formal reasoning tasks like those found in medicine.

This work proposes an architecture that constrains the generative freedom of the LLM through structured prompts which define expected entity types and semantic relations. This controlled output enables the automatic transformation of the resulting ontology into a Bayesian network, establishing conditional dependencies with associated probabilities. The resulting system supports both symbolic and probabilistic inference.

The implementation uses LangChain and ChatGPT via API for ontology extraction, OWLready2 for formal ontology representation, and pgmpy for Bayesian network construction. The system was evaluated on a corpus of eight clinical documents related to oral cancer, successfully generating an interpretable ontology and a functional Bayesian network. Simulated responses demonstrated plausible risk estimates based on combinations of symptoms and observed factors, highlighting the potential of this integration to build decision support tools that not only explain their outputs but also quantify them in a transparent and auditable way.

Index Terms—Ontology learning bayesian networks large language models (LLM) probabilistic inference

I. INTRODUCTION

In domains marked by complex conceptual interdependencies and significant uncertainty, effective decision-making requires tools that extend beyond deterministic logic. Ontologies have long provided a structured way to represent knowledge through formal vocabularies of concepts and relationships. They support tasks like semantic search and knowledge inte-

gration, yet lack mechanisms to model uncertainty—limiting their effectiveness in probabilistic reasoning contexts.

Large Language Models (LLMs) exhibit strong generative capabilities and contextual fluency [2], but their statistical nature and lack of explicit structured knowledge introduce limitations in reliability, transparency, and traceability. These shortcomings are particularly critical in fields like medicine, law, and engineering, where quantitative estimation and causal reasoning are essential.

Fluent language generation alone is insufficient in high-stakes scenarios. Intelligent systems must perform risk assessments, conditional probability evaluations, and scenario analysis. This requires modeling causal dependencies and quantifying uncertainty—tasks that exceed the capabilities of LLMs operating independently. Without structured knowledge, LLM outputs remain ungrounded, constraining their role in decision support.

Recent research addresses these gaps by integrating symbolic knowledge representations—such as taxonomies, knowledge graphs, and ontologies—to guide generation and improve interpretability [1], [3]. Probabilistic ontologies like PR-OWL [8] and BayesOWL [9] extend this further by introducing uncertainty modeling. However, they rely heavily on manual modeling, which limits scalability, and often include abstract relations that complicate probabilistic inference.

Some approaches generate Bayesian networks from logical rules or structured databases [7], while others use data-driven algorithms over curated corpora [6]. These strategies, however, rarely scale to raw, unstructured text—the most abundant and underutilized information source.

We propose a new architecture that leverages LLMs to generate structured probabilistic models directly from domain-specific textual data. Using constrained prompting, LLMs are guided to extract ontologies by identifying key domain entities and semantic relations (e.g., symptoms, causes, effects). These ontologies serve as intermediate, interpretable structures suitable for formal reasoning.

A second LLM module then maps these ontologies to Bayesian Network structures, inferring causal and statistical

dependencies and estimating conditional probabilities from textual evidence. This dual-stage process overcomes LLM limitations by anchoring outputs in symbolic models, while also mitigating the need for manual ontology construction.

The resulting system offers an interpretable and revisable domain model that supports both symbolic and probabilistic reasoning. Users interact through natural language queries, benefiting from the rigor of formal inference grounded in structured domain knowledge.

A. Contributions

This work makes three main contributions: (1) a method to extract ontological structures from domain-specific documents using LLMs; (2) a transformation pipeline that maps these structures into Bayesian networks with estimated conditional dependencies based on textual interpretation; and (3) a mechanism that enables users to perform probabilistic inference via natural language, enhancing decision-making under uncertainty with transparency and interpretability.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed method is implemented through a pipeline that enables a large language model (LLM) to perform probabilistic inference using a Bayesian network automatically derived from domain-specific documents. This section details the system’s usage flow, the automatic construction of the Bayesian network, and the validation procedures applied.

A. LLM-Guided Inference Using a Bayesian Network

A large language model (LLM) enhanced with retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) is complemented by a pre-constructed Bayesian network to enable structured probabilistic inference. This integration is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. System architecture in which a large language model (LLM) coordinates responses by combining two sources of external knowledge: a vector database accessed via retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), and a Bayesian network for structured probabilistic inference. Upon receiving a user query, the LLM first performs a RAG-based retrieval of relevant textual context. It then evaluates whether probabilistic reasoning is required and, if so, queries the Bayesian network to obtain numerical inference results. Finally, all retrieved and computed information is integrated into a coherent natural language response for the user.

The system was implemented using the LangChain framework, which coordinates prompt orchestration and tool execution. The LLM (OpenAI’s ChatGPT) interacts via API and

uses RAG over a FAISS-based vector database to retrieve semantically relevant context from domain-specific documents.

When a user submits a query, the LLM first retrieves relevant textual passages. It then evaluates whether numerical inference is needed and, if so, generates Python code that queries a previously constructed Bayesian network implemented with the `pgmpy` library. This code is executed externally, and the result is integrated into the final response, allowing the LLM to deliver fluent, explainable, and probabilistically grounded answers.

B. Bayesian Network Construction from Structured Knowledge

The process of constructing the Bayesian network is driven by the structured extraction of knowledge from unstructured domain-specific documents. Figure 2 illustrates the full pipeline, including both the ontology generation and the probabilistic model construction stages.

Fig. 2. Pipeline for constructing a Bayesian network from domain-specific documents. A vector database related to a specific topic is queried, and the retrieved content is processed by LLM1 to generate an ontology. This ontology is shaped by a structured prompt (STR1), which defines the classes, semantic relationships, and types of probabilities required. An optional human review step improves accuracy. LLM2 then maps the validated ontology into a Bayesian network suitable for probabilistic inference.

The pipeline begins with the retrieval of domain-relevant content from a vector database built using FAISS. This database is populated with text chunks extracted and embedded from PDF documents using OpenAI embeddings. Once a relevant chunk is retrieved, it is passed to LLM1—an instance of OpenAI’s ChatGPT—through the LangChain framework. LLM1 is responsible for building a formal ontology that captures domain knowledge. This is achieved via a structured prompt known as STR1.

The STR1 prompt serves as a guiding scaffold that limits the degrees of freedom of LLM1 during ontology construction. Without such guidance, automatically generated ontologies tend to exhibit high variability and semantic inconsistency, which impedes their usability in formal reasoning. STR1

defines the types of classes (e.g., "risk factors", "conditions", "symptoms"), relationships (e.g., "causes", "indicates", "precedes"), and expected probabilistic roles. For example, in the domain of oral cancer, STR1 specifies that entities such as tobacco use, alcohol consumption, or poor oral hygiene should be classified as risk factors; "oral cancer" as a condition; and observable features like "persistent ulcers" or "white patches" as symptoms. LLM1 is prompted to extract only instances and relations that conform to this structure and to output a machine-readable ontology using the `Owlready2` Python library.

Importantly, the ontology serves not only as an intermediate representation for probabilistic modeling, but also as a transparent and auditable knowledge layer. It allows domain experts to verify, refine, or dispute the concepts and relationships inferred from the data before they are encoded into a Bayesian network. While STR1 provides a predefined structure for consistency, it is not fixed—different STR1 configurations can be defined for different domains, use cases, or levels of abstraction. The example based on oral cancer is used here to illustrate the approach, but the structure is fully adaptable.

The resulting ontology can optionally be reviewed by a domain expert to correct semantic inconsistencies or fill in missing elements. Once validated, it is passed to LLM2, a second instance of ChatGPT also managed through LangChain. LLM2 is guided by a second STR1-based prompt that instructs it to translate the ontology into a probabilistic model. This prompt specifies the expected directionality of dependencies (e.g., "risk factor → condition → symptom") and the types of nodes to include in the resulting graph.

LLM2 processes the ontology and generates the structure of a Bayesian network, representing variables as nodes and dependencies as directed edges. This structure is instantiated in Python using the `pgmpy` library. To complete the model, conditional probability tables (CPTs) are populated either from frequency estimates derived from the text corpus or from heuristic priors defined by domain experts.

By constraining both LLM1 and LLM2 through STR1, the system ensures compatibility between the ontology and the resulting Bayesian network. This architectural design minimizes ambiguity and simplifies the transformation from semantic knowledge to a formally usable probabilistic model. The integration of ontology-driven design and guided prompts enables the automated construction of a network suitable for inference, explanation, and structured interaction with the LLM.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

All experimental results in this section were obtained using clinical documents related to oral cancer. The pipeline was evaluated end-to-end to extract structured knowledge, generate a Bayesian model, and support probabilistic inference via natural language interaction.

A. Ontology Extraction from Unstructured Text

Using a corpus of eight clinical documents on oral cancer, an LLM guided by a structured prompt (STR1) was used to

generate a domain-specific ontology. The ontology focused on three categories: antecedents, symptoms, and diagnostic targets. The generated structure, shown in Figure 3, includes hierarchical relationships, concept classes, and semantic links. This output served as the basis for subsequent modeling.

Fig. 3. Ontology derived from the oral cancer corpus.

B. Ontology-to-Bayesian Network Transformation

The ontology was automatically transformed into a Bayesian Network by mapping semantic relationships into directed dependencies. The resulting acyclic graph (Figure 4) groups nodes into risk factors, symptoms, and diagnostic outcomes. Conditional probability values were assigned to edges based on co-occurrence in the corpus, available priors, and heuristic assumptions when data was insufficient.

Fig. 4. Bayesian Network derived from the oral cancer corpus, showing conditional dependencies and assigned probability values.

C. Bayesian Reasoning in LLM Interaction

The inference capabilities of the system were evaluated through three test queries using the Bayesian Network. For each case, the system computed posterior probabilities based

on observed factors and returned a simulated natural language response.

Query 1. “*My patient presents with an indurated lesion and persistent pain. What is the likelihood that this is oral cancer?*”

LLM Response: *Estimated probability of oral cancer: 84%.*

Query 2. “*The patient is male, smokes, but has no visible lesions. Should I be concerned about oral cancer?*”

LLM Response: *Estimated probability of oral cancer: 44%.*

Query 3. “*The patient has an exophytic lesion but no pain or history of smoking. How likely is oral cancer?*”

LLM Response: *Estimated probability of oral cancer: 36%.*

These numerical values were obtained using Bayes’ theorem with the conditional and prior probabilities encoded in the Bayesian Network derived from the ontology.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes an integrated framework that transforms unstructured domain-specific text into probabilistic reasoning tools by combining automatic ontology extraction with Bayesian network construction. It addresses the limitations of using ontologies alone (lack of uncertainty modeling) and Bayesian networks alone (need for manual design), by unifying both through large language models (LLMs). The result is an automated pipeline that reduces expert labor while maintaining semantic structure and enabling probabilistic inference.

Unlike earlier systems such as Text2Onto or transformer-based extractors that focus on entity and relation identification, our method goes further by building a functional Bayesian model. This full automation enhances scalability and supports transparent, interpretable reasoning—a crucial advantage in domains like healthcare.

Compared to retrieval-based architectures such as RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation), which offer flexible access to external knowledge but lack structured reasoning mechanisms, our method offers a complementary pathway. While RAG systems return answers based on retrieved fragments, the Bayesian approach allows for explicit inference over causal and correlational structures. This difference opens the door to systematic comparisons in future work. For instance, identical user queries could be answered by both a RAG system and a BN-augmented LLM, allowing quantitative and qualitative assessments of accuracy, consistency, and clinical usefulness.

The results presented in this article are preliminary but encouraging. They show that a small corpus of eight clinical documents was sufficient to induce an interpretable ontology and construct a coherent probabilistic model. Simulated queries illustrated how the system produces plausible, explainable estimates based on combinations of symptoms and risk factors. However, a key limitation remains the estimation of conditional probabilities from limited text. In our pipeline, missing values were handled through heuristic approximations,

which must be refined through expert elicitation or statistical learning in larger datasets.

Future work will focus on validating the accuracy of the inferred probabilities and exploring how different prompting strategies affect ontology structure and model quality. We also plan to generalize the system to support multiple levels of abstraction in the ontology (e.g., temporal events, treatment effects) and more expressive probabilistic structures (e.g., dynamic Bayesian networks). Another important goal is the development of a natural language interface where users can pose questions that are parsed and routed to the Bayesian model. This interface would allow clinicians and non-experts to obtain well-founded, probabilistically coherent answers in everyday language.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the feasibility of integrating LLMs with structured probabilistic modeling in a clinical context. The proposed framework provides a transparent, auditable, and scalable approach for transforming medical literature into decision support tools. By grounding language models in interpretable knowledge representations and equipping them with reasoning capabilities, we take a step toward more trustworthy and actionable AI systems in healthcare.

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